

Neither resistance nor commodification: Madrid's LGBT Pride as a paradoxical mobilization

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ABSTRACT

Pride events and queer spaces have become throughout the years the loci of debates and conflicts. The relationship between emancipatory and mobilized origins, on the one hand, and an evolution towards commodification and mediatization, on the other, have polarized the debate, but for few academic analyses arguing for simultaneous or paradoxical articulations. Madrid's Pride has become one of the most significant events of its kind, experiencing in 2017 a dramatic expansion as it hosted the global World Pride event. This Pride is not free from conflicts, as 2016 Pride's opening act or *pregón* suffered a popular outburst that managed to get the act's main attraction cancelled. This conflict is analyzed as a productive vantage point from which to argue that both resistance and commodification lie within queer spaces and times, as both emancipatory and capitalist practices intersect. The description of the 2016 *pregón* is used in order to argue for a nuanced analysis of the paradoxical duality within queer practices.

KEYWORDS

LGBT Pride, gaybourhoods, resistance, commodification, events

Introduction

An estimate of more than two million visitors made Madrid the global capital of LGBT – lesbian, gay, bisexual, trans – Pride in 2017. The fifth edition of World Pride increased the

political and economic significance of Europe's most visited Pride just a decade after the Spanish capital city hosted Europride. This global event – awarded by the organization Interpride through a bidding system similar to that of Olympic candidacies – involved a joint venture by activists, entrepreneurs and politicians with unequal responsibilities, projects and interests. Different neighborhoods and arenas competed for media attention and public funding, despite the inevitable primacy of Madrid's most famous LGBT space, the neighborhood of Chueca. This scene – which has even become a Spanish synonym of “gay scene” – was the focus of most of the World Pride activities, which included a diverse program of concerts and shows, competitions and stiletto races, as well as a wide range of cultural and social activities organized by the various non-governmental organizations and LGBT associations of the region. Both festive and activist activities and goals intermingled, in anything but a simple way.

Despite the public and private efforts for decentralizing the Pride activities – as Chueca and even Madrid's downtown cannot accommodate all the expected visitors and attendees – this neighborhood is still seen as the central part of Madrid's and even Spain's activist and entrepreneur LGBT environment. The biggest and most visible activist organization, FELGTB,¹ has its headquarters in one of Chueca's streets, next to several ministerial offices and cultural facilities. A nearby square hosts the annual *pregón* or announcement act that sets the Pride festivities into motion. As a well-known activist and politician stated, “[i]t is difficult to imagine Chueca without the Pride and a Pride without Chueca ...” (Carla Antonelli in Ferrando and Córdoba, 2014). Within this central position and role, alternative ideas of sexual freedom, Pride and political emancipation interact. The diversity of agents involved in each year's Pride – entrepreneurs, activists, public administrations, corporate sponsors, media outlets and so on – entail a rich negotiation that is never without conflict or tension.

Two major trends, however, may be seen as opposing constructions. On the one hand, the commodification and mediatization as an extension of Pride events that make them even more appealing. On the other, vindication, emancipation and freedom ideals as the root and original motivation for Pride events. These opposing trends make emancipation – or any alternative *emic* or inner term – a disputed vantage point that is actively negotiated and transformed through the everyday experience of activists, entrepreneurs, citizens, tourists and other stakeholders. This article seeks to contribute to the existing debates, repeated and expanded after most Pride event or after any queer space draws media attention. Within these debates we can find arguments on both the emancipatory and oppressive practices and effects of such queer spaces and times.

This article argues for a common ground between these two competing lines of research and politics, in a specific arena or field: that of Madrid's Pride. I propose the analysis of concrete practices from the perspective of paradoxical negotiation processes. I focus the analysis on the idea of paradox as it allows me to examine both the emancipatory and the exclusionary practices or, rather, to examine each practice as both emancipatory and exclusionary. I follow Gabriel Giorgi (2002, 60) in considering how the market mediation in Chueca and Madrid's Pride “opens pathways across nations and challenges traditional sexual cultures” despite the fact that it also “regulates conditions in which gay identity claims visibility and creates inclusion”.

This article draws from ongoing ethnographic research and the analysis of a significant conflict during 2016 Pride in order to present the paradoxical and negotiated relationship between emancipation and oppression, freedom and control within practices, instead of seeing them as either emancipatory or exclusionary. A popular outburst against a commodified and mediatized *pregón* is examined as a combination of resistance and festivities, vindication and frivolity. I argue that 2016 Madrid's Pride shows that queer

politics are not limited to party or classical politics, demanding a more comprehensive understanding of conflict and negotiation. I also argue that the described conflict shows how both emancipatory and commodifying practices intermingle in Pride events and mobilizations. Just as this line of enquiry has been already considered for various geographical contexts, the specific characteristics of both Madrid and Spain, regarding Pride events, have received considerable attention from academic outlets.²

First, I analyze the recent history of both Chueca and Madrid's Pride in order to highlight the paradoxical relationship between freedom and oppression. Then I narrate the conflict during 2016 Madrid's Pride, describing the actions of several key actors both before and during the *pregón*. I analyze the aforementioned conflict as a significant negotiation of both commodifying and emancipatory practices and ideals, even sharing similar terms of claims. Finally, I present some concluding remarks that aim to argue for a nuanced, complex understanding of the relationship between seemingly contradictory dimensions within queer places and events.

Chueca and Madrid's Pride

Madrid's most visible LGBT space

Chueca is Madrid's most public and well-known LGBT or queer space. It has become synonymous with nearly any queer space within the limits of Spanish culture. The importance of this neighborhood has not escaped the attention of academic researchers. Geographer Emilia García Escalona (2000) was most probably the first scholar to study Chueca, drawing from fieldwork within the neighborhood and from the scrutiny of several key agents' experiences. Gabriel Giorgi's (2002) was probably the first academic article to reflect on Chueca outside the Spanish frontiers. He focused on the perspective of gay tourism and its influence on the image of Madrid, arguing that representations and spaces related to each

other, mirror-like. Two years after Giorgi, Jill Robbins (2004) presented a conference paper highlighting the absence of lesbians in the images and texts that dealt with Chueca.³ More recently, Omar Martinez and Brian Dodge (2010) undertook ethnographic research in Chueca. The events of 2007 EuroPride were the context for one of the most detailed accounts of Chueca, despite several aspects of their research which may seem far-fetched for any frequent attendee to Pride events and everyday Chueca.⁴

As other gayborhoods, Chueca progressively developed from a context of diffuse homosocial practices. Casual sex in public and private spaces gave way to a structured or institutionalized circuit of increasingly linked business and venues (Fernández Salinas 2007; Boivin 2010; Lily 2016). As Boivin (2011) noted, Chueca was the epicenter of a wider area of queer spaces and practices; the middle of a triangle first mentioned by a newspaper in 1985.⁵ During the eighties Chueca was known as a marginal, run-down neighborhood due to drug-trafficking and a significant loss of population: more than a 40 per cent decrease between 1970 and 1991 (von Breyman Miranda 2011; Boivin 2013). The vast majority of accounts explain the change as the nearly miraculous arrival of gay men and lesbians (García Escalona 2000; Veksler 2005), while an increasingly coherent activist discourse has focused on the role of the “desire of visibility” (Pedro Zerolo in Ferrando and Córdoba 2014, 13).

1993 has been used as a likely birthdate of Chueca, as now historic bookstore Berkana moved to the neighborhood. Being the first Spanish bookshop that explicitly focused on queer products, its importance has been described as the birth of a daylight, plain sight experience of homosexuality (Robbins 2004; Herrero Brasas 2007; Ferrando and Córdoba 2014; Lily 2016). The role of Mili Hernández, founder of Berkana and historic activist, has been equated to that of other businesspeople who challenged the now frequent yet interested differentiation between entrepreneurs and activists (Giorgi 2002; Vélez-Pellegrini 2008; Ferrando and Córdoba 2014). She managed to have a starring role in the first massive demonstrations, as a

public figure of historic organization COGAM, while co-creating both the bookshop and Egales, the main LGBT Spanish publisher. As Jill Robbins has explained, this bookstore and her founder adhere to common practices among this type of businesses, given a far more significant attention not to economic mission but to ‘providing a safe space for social, political and cultural events and promoting texts that allow their clientele to frame their experiences and identities so as to better defend their rights’ (2011, 16).

Besides its origins, the evolution and present state of Chueca has also been increasingly researched. Martínez and Dodge (2010) state how Chueca grew to be the most important queer enclave in Spain, while Juan José Ortega Román (2007) spoke of the neighborhood as a geographical synecdoche: a term that represents everything that is LGBT-related in Madrid or even Spain. The particularity of Chueca's concentration of queer venues has also been noted (Giorgi 2002; Boivin 2010), just as its comparatively less significant residential concentration (Fuentes 2007). The role of gentrification in Chueca – and of queer people in gentrification – has been analyzed from various perspectives (Villaamil 2004; von Breyman Miranda 2011; García Pérez 2014; Domínguez Ruiz 2016), either on their own or in relation with radical activist critiques towards the scene (Petit 2003; Vélez-Pellegrini 2008).

MADO: Madrid's Pride

MADO,⁶ Madrid's officially sanctioned Pride, is the city's most visited and relevant event in terms of tourism, revenue and politics. It is the main local link or homage to the Stonewall riots, the pretext of most Pride events (Kates and Belk 2001; Luongo 2002; Petit 2003; Hughes 2006). Madrid has hosted Pride marches, demonstrations and parades since 1978, one year after the first Spanish demonstration, in Barcelona (Ferrando and Córdoba 2014; Lily 2016). The term used to name Madrid's Pride – march, demonstration, parade, *fiesta*, etcetera⁷

– is of political significance, as anthropologist and Pride expert Begonya Enguix (2009) has noted. These terms do not modify, however, the queering or subversive role, either more or less temporary, of Pride events, as Lynda Johnston (2001, 2007) has argued.

Madrid's, as other Pride events, has “a decidedly syncretic nature” (Kates and Belk 2001, 393). It is organized by an alliance of activist organizations – COGAM as the historic Madrid association and FELGTB as the State-level federation – with entrepreneurs and, more recently, with the financial and logistic support of public administrations (Petit 2003). COGAM is the main organizer of the demonstration, controlling even the order of official demonstrators and floats (Enguix 2009, 2017). It is joined by other fellow organizations within FELGTB, as well as political parties, trade unions, businesses and so on. Besides the demonstration, the festive part – with an extensive schedule of shows, cultural activities and concerts – is managed by AEGAL, as the association of LGBT businesspeople from Madrid.

The alliance between activists and entrepreneurs, despite several critiques, has proven to be effective: the attendance at the annual demonstration dramatically increased since the first float was used in 1996, sparking a still-ongoing debate on commodification and vindication (Ferrando and Córdoba 2014; Lily 2016; Enguix 2017). Several changes regarding the itinerary have also affected the number and variety of attendees (Villaamil 2004), but, as with other Pride events, the carnivalization or festivalization of the demonstration is held responsible for the attendance increase (Kates and Belk 2001; Hughes 2006). This carnivalization has provoked not only intense political debates and critiques in (Coll-Planas 2012; Enguix 2017) but also academic analyses of the *duality* of Pride events, as in *both* politics and festivity (Waitt and Markwell 2006; Enguix 2009). I follow this line of enquiry. Assuming that merchandise and leisure consumption are an inherent aspect of the participation in Pride events, as Kates and Belk (2001) stated, the issue at hand is to analyze how and to what ends does consumption play a role in Chueca and Madrid's Pride. With this

aim in mind, I find Eric Olson's analysis of Pride events' sponsors of particular usefulness. He noted how several factors increasingly affect contemporary pride events: “[g]lobalization, the increase in heterosexuals as event attendees (as allied and spectators), a focus on niche markets with the pride umbrella, and the increased use of sponsorship” (Olson 2016, 5).

The reference to 2017 World Pride, as a global event of activist origins and consequences, may be seen as an explicit recognition of an otherwise ignored dimension of MADO and nearly any other Pride event in Europe: the transnational origin of various symbolic and functional aspects, such as the demonstration’s date, as well as the Pride flags and many of the claims and chants. Phillip Ayoub (2016, 2) has highlighted in a recent book how “[v]isibility for LGBT people often has its roots in transnational sources”. The inevitable reference to New York and the Stonewall Riots and the presence of Gilbert Baker’s rainbow flag is of the vernacularizing process that combines and shapes local and global symbols and contents (García Escalona 2000; Martinez and Dodge 2010). From a narrow political perspective, considering simply the activist organizations and their alliances with political parties and trade unions, the transnational influence of Pride events and politics is also evident. The global and European dimension of 2017 World Pride, as well as other previous events, makes MADO a part of an European understanding and practice of LGBT activism. Ayoub (2016) has analyzed the increasing role of European politics and transnational examples and practices in local movements, including the access to advocacy networks, strategies, but also asymmetrical relationships between leading and follower states or regions.

This Pride’s success has not lacked its critiques and explicit alternative and opponents. The most well-known alternative project is that of Madrid’s *Orgullo Crítico* or Critical Pride. This movement has become characterized by its links with queer identities and theory, as well as to a notion of intersectionality and of alliances with other political movements, such as pro-immigrant, pro-prostitutes and *Indignado* groups.⁸ This movement acquired political and

media visibility due to its critiques to mainstream MADO, although it has roots in several LGBT and queer movements in the nineties, such as *LSD* and *Radical Gai*.⁹ It must be highlighted the spatial and temporal distinction that, as of 2018, the *Orgullo Crítico* still makes. Whereas the mainstream MADO march takes place always on Saturday, the critical demonstration always takes places on June 28. This demonstration avoids its alternative's spaces for demonstrating, choosing to create a different symbolic space of queerness. Depending on the year, this demonstration has taken the queer visibility to working-class districts far from Downtown Madrid, while in more recent times it has reached the symbolic center of the city after crossing neighborhoods well-known for their immigrant population and movements. 2017 World Pride was also an occasion for heightened critiques from this movements,¹⁰ as well as an opportunity for joining forces as a *Orgullo de Periferia* or Periphery Pride.¹¹

2016 *pregón*: fighting for and along freedom

Wednesday. 29 June 2016, 7 p.m. Several hundred people fill Pedro Zerolo¹² square in Chueca. The streets that lead to the square have been controlled by the police for a couple of hours while several TV camera crews have been setting a platform facing the main stage. One of Madrid's most well-known drag queens, Plexi, starts a monologue with frequent references to the many years she has been entertaining the stage of the Pride's *pregón* or starting announcement.¹³ After several minutes two men appear on the stage, half an hour behind schedule. Juan Carlos Alonso and Alfonso Llopart are two of the most visible members of AEGAL, the LGBT business association of Madrid's region. They appear as heads of the organization that manages the festive dimension of Madrid's Pride, being responsible for most of the event with the exception of the demonstration that would take place three days later. They give a speech on the importance of Madrid's Pride, its evolution and the key role of

recently deceased activist Pedro Zerolo. After several claims that are answered with cheers and applause, they introduce the two co-presidents of InterPride, the organization that holds and grants the World Pride brand.

They introduce thus the following year's event, for which 2016 is but a general drill, an opportunity to show the readiness of both the city and the business association. The crowd cheers and applauds when the screen on the stage plays a video from Pride Orlando colleagues, thanking the homage and award they are receiving from Madrid's Pride organizers and community. "Orlando! Orlando! Orlando!" starts as a lonely call but progressively turns into a massive outcry, a reminder of the recent massacre.¹⁴ A local singer enacts a further homage to Orlando, presenting a brand-new song to remember the fallen LGBT people. Alonso and Llopart remember once more the historical importance of Spanish activist Pedro Zerolo, whose political activities were crucial in order to achieve equal marriage on a state level in 2005. They introduce the activist organizations that were Zerolo's home and life: COGAM, Madrid's historical LGBT association, and FELGTB, the federation in which the former is included. Activists from both organizations appear onstage, several of them wearing the bisexual flag – pink, lavender and blue – as for them 2016 is themed around this sexual orientation. A lesbian activist from COGAM comments on the recent queer bashings on Madrid's streets whilst FELGTB's executive board members advocate for state-level LGBT legislation and for bisexual visibility. The activists stay onstage as the screen plays a short film on Pride and while its director is publicly awarded and acclaimed by the business association's members. Finally, three sportspeople who are out and proud appear onstage as key visible examples of visibility, for which they are also awarded.

Most of the crowd attending the 2016 *pregón* experienced it as a planned performance of pride, visibility and anticipation for 2017 World Pride, as well as a celebration of departed activists and LGBT people. This *pregón* continued years of tradition. The *pregón* or public

announcements on Wednesday signaled the beginning of Pride week in Madrid and made visible and explicit the activist core or origin of the march or demonstration taking place on Saturday. Other conventional elements were seen in previous years: a performance by the traditionally entertaining drag Plexi, as well as the participation of key activist organizations. Crowds of different ages, gender identities, sexual orientations and languages laughed, drank and partied as usual. Groups and couples sat under public art and lamp posts. Several bars in front of restaurants, hotels and shops served drinks at a fixed price while police officers controlled the entrances to this and other spaces, looking for bottles. Madrid's Pride seemed to be business as usual. Its *pregón* seemed to be the spark giving way to half a week of parties, shows and other cultural activities.

Despite appearances, the *pregón* experienced a dramatic change of plans few days before it took place. The main attraction, as it has been common practice in previous years, was the *pregón* by famous men or women who spoke on behalf of the organization. The jury of TV show MasterChef, restaurateurs Jordi Cruz, Pepe Rodríguez and Samantha Vallejo-Nágera, were the announced *pregoneros* – literally: town criers or bellmen – who would ignite the events. They would continue the tradition of having a celebrity read a manifesto regarding the state of LGBT rights and Madrid's Pride, as well as aiming to empower and amuse the attendees. Before them, a centric plaza of Chueca had already hosted singers, actors and actresses, film directors and journalists, LGBT or not, always joined by popular drag queens as well as activist and business leaders from COGAM, FELGTB and AEGAL.

One week before the date, an online queer media outlet, *Estoy Bailando*, issued an article regarding the announcement of the MasterChef *pregoneros*. With their usual witty and cheeky style, the site described the jury's being chosen as an utter surprise due to the lack of known records of them contributing in any way to the LGBT cause.¹⁵ *Estoy Bailando* explicitly claimed that no restaurateur nor cooking show needs to be a vocal advocate, existing a wide

range of alternative sources of famous people. What is more, *Estoy Bailando* reviewed a series of sexist and even homophobic stereotypes and jokes reproduced by the famous TV show jury. The website elaborated their vindication, enumerating a series of queer bashings occurred in Madrid in 2015 and 2016, as well as other activist needs and requests. They analyzed the polemic decision as part of the commercializing and festivalizing tendency of Madrid's Pride, directly linked to the role of the businesspeople involved – in other words, AEGAL. *Estoy Bailando* even dealt with the responsibility of the activist associations that participate in the organization of the Pride, as direct or indirect collaborators.

Estoy Bailando's article was an immediate success and was followed the very next day – June the 23rd – by the proposal of a direct action, as well as by an update: after contacting AEGAL and the activist organizations, they had had no response.¹⁶ On their second article they shared a Change.org petition that called for AEGAL to cancel the MasterChef *pregón*. The petition's author asked for alternative *pregoneros*, to whom LGBT people could feel more related. Their proposal mobilized more than 10,000 supporters in a few hours.¹⁷ Besides this petition, *Estoy Bailando* came up with an additional idea: to convene a popular *cacerolada* for the *pregón*. They asked their followers to take their pans and pots – *cacerolas* – in order to loudly bang them as a protest. *Caceroladas* are a frequent form of resistance in Spanish cities, combining both a deafening noise and an impressive crowd. In their usual cynical tone, *Estoy Bailando* suggested to dress up the *cacerolada* as a support act for the restaurateurs:

¡A la mierda el Orgullo! ¡Convirtamos la Plaza Pedro Zerolo en la fiesta de la cocina!
No te digo que montemos una guerra de comida o nos pongamos a preparar bocadillos de salchichón reconstruido, pero si los de AEGAL creen que estos tres nos representan... ¡No les dejemos en la estacada! ¡CACEROLADA POPULAR!
Es por esto que desde Estoybailando.com *te invitamos a venir al pregón del Orgullo de Madrid con tu utensilio favorito de cocina para hacer mucho ruido durante el pregón y demostrar lo mucho que amamos la alta cocina. A ser posible pídele a tu madre o a tu*

abuela o a tu tía Paqui las cacerolas, sartenes y *productos oficiales de Masterchef* ¡para que AEGAL vea que han acertado de pleno con la elección de los *pregoneros*! ¡¡Porque todos los gays nos sentimos muy identificados con los cocineros heterosexuales!! (emphasis in original)¹⁸

A few hours later *Estoy Bailando* issued a third article on the *pregón*, announcing that AEGAL had cancelled it.¹⁹ With a succinct statement, the LGBT business association claimed that the media storm had made them see they had hurt many people's feelings. As such, they had decided to cancel the *pregón*, keeping the rest of the event as planned. In other words: there would more or less be a *pregón*, without *pregoneros*. A few days later – June the 28th – the media site published a final article reviewing what had happened during that intense week.²⁰ They claimed how AEGAL, instead of choosing other *pregoneros*, cancelled the event visibly proving the appropriation of Madrid's Pride by entrepreneurs and business moguls. *Estoy Bailando* also challenged the argument of “heterophobia” used by various queer media outlets who defended both AEGAL and their MasterChef jury. As the website notes, several straight celebrities had already been *pregoneros* with no public outburst or critiques whatsoever.

In 2016, however, the issue or debate was not the sexual orientation of those chosen by the organization, but the “la evidente estrategia comercial que iba a volver a convertir en un anuncio el *pregón* del Orgullo de Madrid; en una telepromoción, en una mierda sin sentido y sin reivindicación alguna”.²¹ As *Estoy Bailando* reviewed, many arguments were used in order to advocate for the cancelled *pregón*, including the aforementioned claim of “heterophobia”. The main spokesperson from AEGAL regarding Madrid Pride defended their decision as a matter of freedom of speech, as well as a consequence of the vindication of freedom of all kind that is inherent to Pride events worldwide. He argued for his association's

historical engagement and defense of freedom in all its possible forms, being this outcry a case of self-censorship or policing.

Thus, *freedom* explicitly appeared under the spotlight. On the one hand: vindication, freedom and activism understood as the opposition to a commodified *pregón*. On the other hand: straight allies, corporate sponsors and media attention understood as freedom of speech and Pride. *Freedom* of speech and the traditionally used *emancipation* became battle lines along which different notions and projects of Chueca and Pride were mobilized. Madrid's Pride explicitly became a disputed idea, caught between two possible tendencies or movements regarding queer spaces and times. Between the battle lines, a series of activist organizations and key activists, caught under the crossfire of the seemingly only options: commodification or vindication.

The 2016 *pregón*: negotiating the boundaries and contents of freedom

Following Fernando Villaamil (2004), Lynda Johnston (2007) and Begonya Enguix (2009, 2017), I agree with Kath Browne's (2007) argument that queer or non-straight times and spaces are particularly productive vantage points from which to analyze contradictions, tensions or, simply, relations between seemingly contradictory concepts and discourses. From this standpoint I aim to consider not simply that Chueca and Madrid's Pride are the foci of these contradictions or tensions but, rather, that the study of these places and events as paradoxes or as part of a paradoxical relationship allows us to account for the seemingly contradictory adscription of Pride events as *both* resistance *and* commodification. For this matter it is necessary to highlight how late did the Spanish LGBT activist movement gain momentum, compared to other nearby countries (Martínez 2017).

I aim to analyze a concrete conflict that took place at the beginning of 2016 Madrid's Pride: the aforementioned *pregón*. This conflict is analyzed as an empiric episode which may

be productively dissected as *both* resistance *and* consumption, a controlled outburst mediated by the festivalized and plausible outlets, yet an expression of an ideal of sexual, political and economic freedom nevertheless. My analysis follows Kath Browne's (2007) argument as I understand that these tensions are spatially focused or specific. *Estoy Bailando's* analysis and critique derived from the already mentioned line of enquiry that questions the commodification of Pride events and, more particularly, of Chueca and Madrid's Pride. The three organizing associations – AEGAL, COGAM and FELGTB – are accused of trying to control the outcome of Pride and mobilization, whether for economic or political reasons, while corporate sponsors and even conservative politicians adapt to Madrid's Pride.²² These critiques are not new, and they may have peaked in 2011, several months after the *15M* or Spanish Occupy movement.

These critiques and, more overtly, the popular outburst against the MasterChef *pregón* may be seen as contradicting a depoliticizing tendency noted by several scholars and activists. Aliaga and Cortés (2000) commented, referring to the Spanish context, how the mobilization of the queer community was reduced to partying every June the 28th. Òscar Guasch (2007) argued along the same lines, claiming that such politicization entailed the transformation of queer people – particularly gay men – into numb consumers. Beatriz Gimeno (2005), a historic lesbian and feminist activist, commented the same regarding the current state of Spanish lesbians. Finally, queer theoretician and activist Paco Vidarte (2010) equated this depoliticizing trend with that of assimilation to heteronormativity or heterosexual structures. Following this perspective, recently departed activist Shangay Lily (2002, 2016) minted the term *burgayses* as a portmanteau of bourgeois and gay, referring to gay men who exemplify the already extensively researched relationship between assimilation and market forces (Rushbrook 2002; McRuer 2006; Ghaziani 2011).

Despite these analyses, the experience of the threat of a *cacerolada* and the cancellation of the MasterChef *pregón* may be used as evidence of resistance practices and of the negotiated nature of emancipation and mobilization within the context of Pride and gayborhoods. The *cacerolada* must be seen as a clear resistance practice, if we are to follow Sidney Tarrow's definition of protest: a "disruptive collective action that is aimed at institutions, elites, authorities, or other groups, on behalf of the collective goals of the actors or those they claim to represent" (1991, 11). Resistance or protest, however, does not exist in a social void: it is a series of diverse practices within a sociocultural specific reality. What results, following anthropologist George Marcus (1998, 61), may be seen as "a compromise between a mix of elements of resistance to incorporation into a larger whole and of elements of accommodation to this larger order".

It is this end product, the outcome of this negotiation, what I aim to consider. As Kath Browne (2007, 67), I argue that "[i]t is not only the intent of the organizers (or the readings of academics) that create Pride politics". The entrepreneur organizers do not have the monopoly over the definition of freedom, either sexual, political, or cultural within these events and spaces. Neither does the institutionalized activists, nor the media outlets such as *Estoy Bailando*. The different meanings given to Pride and Chueca are but lines of thought and political intent that intersect and, far more interestingly, produce a negotiated outcome that changes not simply every year but nearly for every event, space or concrete context.

Estoy Bailando may be an outsider to the main media outlets regarding Madrid's Pride and Chueca, but they work in a similar vein, participate in analogous contexts and produce a comparable coverage of these events. Following the aforementioned comments on the relationship between resistance and consumption, I argue that the very same mediatization that allows the (at least attempted) commodification of Chueca and Madrid's Pride also empowers critiques and struggles for (another) freedom with similar tools. Paraphrasing

Jasbir Puar's (2002, 111) comment on consumption and resistance, I claim that it would be a mistake to assume that this kind of mediatization and banalization is not a sign of resistance and struggle for (some kind of) freedom. The visibility of the current Pride event in Madrid, despite its differences regarding the 1970's and 1980's demonstrations, is nevertheless a significant political effort that introduces non-straight themes, peoples and concepts within media outlets and political debates. As such, I argue that despite how banal, festive and commodified Madrid's Pride might be seen as of 2016, it is a political-activist event that draws from specific discourses of freedom, visibility, involvement and politics.

The not-so-recent history of Madrid's Pride gives us more arguments following the same line of thought. In 2011 the main concerts were evicted from centric squares in Chueca due to a noise restriction, sparking a popular outburst similar to the one convened in 2016. Then-mayor Alberto Ruiz-Gallardón stumbled upon dozens of angry queer citizens participating in a *cacerolada* at his doorstep when he tried to walk his dog.²³ Despite not being able to revert the public administration's decision, this upheaval was nevertheless remembered as evidence of the political and mobilizing soul of Pride events, however festivalized. This eruption of collective anger may have been a reaction to a change in the music and party's location, but it was a political action nonetheless. Spanish queers may only mobilize for their/our annual party, as Aliaga and Cortés (2000) stated, but mobilization it is. Similarly, the 2016 threat to boycott the *pregón* banging pots and pans might have been a reaction to an already commodified, mediatized event.²⁴ It was still a key political moment and a reminder of the duality of queer spaces and times.²⁵

It must be noted how this particular two episodes of street and social network struggle in Chueca and its Pride may be understood within a contemporary context of new or renewed forms of protest, following the decline of what Guillem Martínez (2012) has called the *Culture of the Transition*. Victor Sampedro and Josep Lobera (2014) have used Martínez's

perspective on this *culture* as a vantage point from which to understand the cycle of protests best illustrated by 2011 Indignado or 15M movement. Sampedro and Lobera argue that the political and cultural consensus that formed the *Transición* as a political era was precisely questioned by the aforementioned protest movement. Dissent, widely and diversely understood, was thus the epicenter of such a movement that has permeated into Spanish politics, exemplified by the creation or renewal of political parties and movement different from the already existing ones. This movement has also permeated or echoed among the forms of protest: as Eduardo Romanos (2016) argued, the 15M movement proved that in the Spanish context protest and humor may be simultaneous and even reinforce each other. However, and as Ricardo Méndez (2012) explained for the specific case of Madrid, these forms of struggle may not be articulated or organized enough as to counter the existing neoliberal urban and political system in Spain and Madrid.

Concluding remarks

The central position of Chueca and Madrid's Pride within both the city and the LGBT scene and arena has been highlighted throughout this article as a means and cause of tension and conflict. The expected millions – both of visitors and of euros – that flood Madrid on an annual basis are also the context of constant negotiations between differing yet not necessarily incompatible political, cultural and economic projects. This article has aimed to argue that such a conflictive nature of Pride space and time may be productively analyzed not as resistance *or* commodification, but rather as *both* of them, or as a negotiated outcome of their interplay. The State-level annual demonstration is a key example of the simultaneity of market forces and queer vindication as struggles or movements towards ideas of freedom. On the one hand, the commodification and mediatization of the demonstration – beginning with its first float in 1996 – is advocated from the perspective of the increase of attendees and,

consequently, of inspired, empowered and festive people. On the other hand, the vindication core of the demonstration is highlighted as a contextual political tool aimed annually towards particular causes or needs.

Chueca's visibility and importance may be stated analogously. A commodified or gentrified presence has given the gayborhood a public and media visibility that would have been otherwise unthinkable, making it a more relevant lighthouse for queer people, yet at the same time an increasingly exclusive locus, expensive as both a residential and a leisure neighborhood. Its *pregón* may have been progressively commodified, reaching a peak in 2014 when it was partially turned into a commercial for a private party whose main star was one of the *pregoneros*, Eurovision Song Contest winner Conchita Wurst.²⁶ However, it was this singer's publicity which broadcasted the *pregón's* emancipatory and proud content to a wider audience. Regarding both the *pregón* and the demonstration, just as with the Pride festivities and with the everyday activities within Chueca, I have concluded that it is an analytic mistake to categorically separate or oppose vindication and market forces, the struggle towards freedom(s) and the commodification of queer times and spaces. I have rather focused on the nuanced consideration of concrete practices, highlighting how emancipation and oppression, most frequently seen as activism and commodification, constantly interplay and negotiate.

Instead of seeing particular events and practices as *either* freedom or oppression, I have advocated analyzing the complementary and simultaneous dimensions within each particular event. Alternative notions of Pride, sexual freedom and social and cultural empowerment and emancipation are constantly intersecting within each practice in queer times and spaces, explicitly conflictive or not. As I have noted, similar discourses may be employed as arguments for or against seemingly opposing positions regarding gayborhoods and Pride events. While this may complicate a simple, dichotomous distinction, it hints at an analytical strategy that was followed throughout this article: not to consider freedom or

emancipation a categorically and easily defined reality but, rather, to acknowledge the inherent duality of LGBT times and spaces, as well as politics, and to search for the specific role that freedom dynamically plays as it relates to seemingly contradictory material and discursive practices.

It is no surprise that Spanish queer arenas or scenes show the same paradoxical nature that has been noted by analysts in other geographical contexts. Just as Madrid's Pride shares Stonewall's nearly sacred date, this event participates from the very same range of conflicts: increasing commodification, the participation of entrepreneurs, corporate sponsors and public administrations, or the apparent duality between activism and party, vindication and market drives. What in fact is specific to the Spanish state is the pace or speed with which its LGBT movement has grown into one of the most successful queer social movements in Western contexts, regarding legal victories and public visibility.

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Biographical note

Currently a PhD candidate in the Universidad Autónoma de Madrid's Social Anthropology Department, his academic career has focused on the intersection of urban studies, gender and queer studies and tourism. His academic publications, as of today, have focused on LGBT Pride events and their urban distribution, as well as on biphobia and LGBT activism. He has also been a participant in Spain- and Madrid-based LGBT activist organizations.

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Notes

- ¹ *Federación Estatal de Lesbianas, Gais, Transexuales y Bisexuales*, or State Federation of Lesbian, Gay, Trans and Bisexual people. It should be noted that the LGBT acronym is usually written differently in Spain due to the Federation's late acceptance of bisexuality. It should also be noted that transsexuality is more widely used as an umbrella term than transgenderism in Spain.
- ² Relevant scholars such as Jill Robbins (2004, 2011), Fernando Villaamil (2004), Juan A. Herrero Brasas (2001, 2007), Alberto Mira (2002) or Ricardo Llamas and Paco Vidarte (1999) have researched and theorized about Chueca and its political, economic and geographical dimensions.
- ³ Robbins further developed her study about Chueca as a book published in 2011. It is a particularly insightful account of the cultural – specifically literary – evolution of lesbian representation in Madrid.
- ⁴ Martinez and Dodge analyse the lack of *flamenco* shows as evidence of the resistance of Spanish tradition, while the seemingly ubiquitous presence of a rainbow-flagged Spanish bull is described as an appropriation or vernacularization of international queer symbols. Having frequently visited Chueca since 2009 – on a nearly weekly basis – and having intensively researched the neighbourhood since 2015, I have never found any rainbow-flagged bull, nor have I considered the significance of the lack of *flamenco* within the context of Madrid, as this dance has never been a traditional one but, rather, a tourism-related import from southern Spain. It should be noted, nevertheless, that the tradition of a *pregón* even for Madrid's Pride reaffirms the public, collective and even traditional nature of the event. On the one hand, this *pregón* makes Spanish tradition a little bit queer. On the other, it makes this event a part of centuries-old traditions.
- ⁵ Javier Rivas in *El País*, September 8, 1985.
https://elpais.com/diario/1985/09/08/sociedad/494978405_850215.html
- ⁶ MADO stands for Madrid Orgullo, or Madrid Pride.
- ⁷ The official name of the Pride march is *State LGTB demonstration*, due to the fact that FELGTB convenes the event on a State level. The early 2000s witnessed the transformation of the then-local Pride into a State level event as a key political weapon for LGBT associations and political parties (Gimeno 2007; Enguix 2017). It should be noted that among Spanish left-wing and critical movements, the term *State* is preferred to *nation*.
- ⁸ The *Indignado* or *15M* movement was and is the Spanish vernacularization of the Arab Spring and the Occupy Movements. Its most visible action was the occupation of Madrid's Puerta del Sol

square in 2011. As of 2018 its effects are still visible in mainstream politics, as well as in grassroots movements.

⁹ LSD and Radical Gai were founded or co-founded by former members of now mainstream associations such as COGAM in Madrid. They used direct actions and political critiques that mirrored those of Queer Nation or ACT UP. Ramón Martínez (2017) and Gracia Trujillo (2008) have both explained the history and activities of such movements in Spain.

¹⁰ https://www.eldiario.es/sociedad/Orgullo-Critico-multitudinaria-World-Pride_0_659334397.html (accessed 12/04/18)

¹¹ http://cadenaser.com/emisora/2017/06/06/radio_madrid/1496750344_383648.html (accessed 12/04/18)

¹² Pedro Zerolo was a key LGBT activist in Madrid, as well as a city council member on behalf of the socialist party. He was one of the most public activists who advocated for equal marriage. A square in Chueca, previously named Vázquez de Mella after a nineteenth century conservative politician, was renamed after the activist's death in 2015.

¹³ The *pregón* is a traditional institution in public fairs and festivities throughout Spain. *Pregoneros* or town-criers were a centuries-old form of public communication, key as a means to publicize official edicts and news. They used to loudly cry the news from town or city squares in order to reach everyone. In recent times the *pregón* is still widely used to start public events and, more specifically, local festivities such as *San Isidro*, Madrid's patron saint. The fact that MADO starts with a *pregón* is a key element in the public – at least collective – nature of Madrid's Pride.

¹⁴ On June 12, 2016, almost fifty people were killed in a terrorist shooting in Pulse, a nightclub in Orlando, Florida. More than fifty people were injured by the perpetrator, who was shot by the police after a long standoff. Most of the victims were Latino LGBT people, and this massacre was thus seen as the most recent act of mass violence against queer people.

¹⁵ <http://estoybailando.com/que-cono-hacen-los-de-masterchef-dando-el-pregon-del-orgullo-de-madrid/> (accessed 10/02/17)

¹⁶ <http://estoybailando.com/cacerolada-popular-convierte-el-pregon-del-orgullo-de-masterchef-en-una-fiesta-de-la-cocina/> (accessed 10/02/17)

¹⁷ <https://www.change.org/p/no-al-jurado-de-masterchef-como-pregoneros-del-orgullo-de-madrid-2016-no-nos-representan> (accessed 10/02/17)

¹⁸ To hell with Pride! *Let's turn Plaza Pedro Zerolo into the kitchen party!* I'm not asking you to spark a food fight or to start preparing reconstructed salchichón¹⁸ sandwiches, but if those from AEGAL think that these three [restaurateurs] represent us... We can't leave them behind! **POPULAR CACEROLADA!** It is for this reason that Estoybailando.com *invites you to visit Madrid's Pride*

pregón with your favorite kitchenware in order to make a lot of noise during the pregón proving how much we love haute cuisine. If possible ask your mother or your grandmother or your aunt Paqui for pots, pans and *official MasterChef merchandise*, so AEGAL can see they have made the right decision choosing the pregoneros! Because we gays are very identified with straight cooks!

¹⁹ <http://estoybailando.com/cancelado-el-pregon-del-orgullo-de-masterchef-en-madrid/>

²⁰ <http://estoybailando.com/un-orgullo-sin-pregon-o-de-como-aegal-y-el-mado-se-rien-de-ti-en-tu-cara/> (accessed 10/02/17)

²¹ “evident commercial strategy that would turn Madrid's Pride *pregón* into an advertisement; into a marketing promotion, into shit with no sense nor vindication”. <http://estoybailando.com/un-orgullo-sin-pregon-o-de-como-aegal-y-el-mado-se-rien-de-ti-en-tu-cara/> (accessed 10/02/17)

²² <http://estoybailando.com/esperanza-aguirre-orgullo-gay-gran-via/> (accessed 10/02/17)

²³ <http://www.abc.es/20110614/local-madrid/abci-cacerolada-gallardon-201106140941.html> (accessed 10/02/17)

²⁴ As *Estoy Bailando* noticed, the 2015 *pregón* by Eurovision Song Contest Conchita Wurst was evidence enough of this commodification, as she promoted a private show that would be taking place during Pride week.

²⁵ The work of David Bell and Jon Binnie (2004, 2006) – also in Bell (1995), Binnie (2016), Binnie and Valentine (1999) and, above all, Bell and Valentine (1995) – has laid the foundation for a geographical understanding of gender and sex diversity. They have productively acknowledged the role of different notions of citizenship in the spatial nature of sexuality, as well as the key intersection of diverse scales. Regarding time, Natalie Oswin (2012) has analyzed the lack of queerness in planned conceptions of time, using the empirical case of Singapore.

²⁶ <https://www.madridiario.es/noticia/413303/social/conchita-wurst-la-actuacion-mas-esperada-del-shangay-pride-2014.html> (accessed 10/02/17)